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Authors	
Name	Partner
Célia Dupain	IC
Ernest Nadal	ICO
Mireia Gausachs	ICO
Carles Codony	ICO
Zeina Chamoun-Morel	IC

Contributors	
Name	Partner
Nancy Frédérickx	Sciensano

Summary and objective of the deliverable

With the growing number of targeted therapies approved for the same indication in oncology and the increasing complexity of tumour profiles, molecular screening programs have been more widely implemented in clinical routine.

Molecular Tumor Boards (MTBs) play a critical role in precision oncology by matching patients to therapies, particularly when standard treatment guidelines are absent. They bring together expertise in oncology, genomics, pathology, and bioinformatics to analyze tumor profiles and identify actionable genomic alterations that can guide therapeutic decisions. MTBs often recommend non-standard or tumor-agnostic treatments based on molecular alterations, especially when standard options have been exhausted. By fostering collaborative decision-making and incorporating cutting-edge genomic insights, MTBs ensure equitable access to personalized treatment opportunities for all cancer patients.

Deliverable 8.4 aims to provide an overview of the number of patients oriented towards personalized treatment, after MTB discussion.

Work performed

To gain an understanding of the number of patients directed toward personalized treatment, three main actions were implemented:

I - A survey was developed in collaboration with WP9 (Treatment and Follow-up) and WP10 (Oncology Decision Support Tools) across the CanHeal consortium to map current practices on diagnostic and therapeutic practices related to:

- i) NGS ‘wet lab’ and ‘dry lab’,
- ii) Molecular Tumour Board (MTB),
- iii) Oncology Decision support tool (oncDST) and
- iv) Regulatory, economic and healthcare policy aspects of NGS.

The survey results were integrated with insights from Deliverable D8.1 (Description of various MTB organizations, applied NGS panel types, and patient selection criteria across Europe) and D8.2 (National initiatives for genome-wide tumor characterization).

II - An independent survey, designed by ICO, was disseminated through the Spanish Lung Cancer Group (GECP).

III - A survey of the literature reporting clinical studies integrating NGS analysis and MTB discussion was conducted.

Results

I. Collaborative (WPs 8, 9, 10) survey results

The data presented in this paragraph is derived from the collaborative survey conducted by CanHeal WPs 8, 9, and 10, with detailed results available in Annex I. The survey achieved significant success with 116 responses from across Europe. This included participants from 14 EU member countries and 3 non-EU countries: Serbia, Norway, and England. Out of the 116 respondents, 75 (65%) reported participation in one or more MTBs. 54 unique MTBs were identified, with detailed information available for 49 of them. Among these, patient outcomes and related statistics were reported for 13 MTBs, listed in Figure 1.

COUNTRY	MTB code	Geographical scope	MTB Name	Participating Institutes
BELGIUM	BEMTB01	National	Belgian PRECISION national Molecular Tumor Board (nMTB) (BALLETT/GeNeo)	AZ Delta
				Ghent University Hospital
				Grand Hôpital de Charleroi GHDC
				IPG
				Institut Jules Bordet
				Jessa Hospital
				UZ Leuven
GERMANY	DEMTB05	Local	MTB of the UKSH	UKSH
				UKSH Kiel
FRANCE	FRMTB05	National	Refractory or Relapse Acute leukemia	Hematology laboratory Hôpital Saint-Louis, Assistance Publique-Hôpitaux de Paris (AP-HP); Université Paris-Cité
FRANCE	FRMTB06	Multi-institutional	Réunion transversale de Biologie moléculaire PACA-Est	Centre Antoine Lacassagne
FRANCE	FRMTB08	National	RCP CUP (carcinoma of unknown primary)	AP-HP (Assistance Publique-Hôpitaux de Paris-Hopital Cochin)
				Institut Curie
ITALY	ITMTB03	Local	IRE MTB	Regina Elena National Cancer Institute - IRCCS
ITALY	ITMTB04	Local	local MTB at Candiolo IRCC FPO	IRCCS FPO Candiolo
ITALY	ITMTB06	Multi-institutional	MTB Policlinico Gemelli	Fondazione Policlinico Universitario Gemelli - IRCCS
ITALY	ITMTB07	Multi-institutional	Region Puglia MTB	IRCCS Istituto Tumori Giovanni Paolo II
ITALY	ITMTB08	Multi-institutional	Regional MTB of Lombardy	Istituto Europeo di Oncologia IRCCS

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SPAIN	ESMTB01	Local	MTB Catalan Institute of Oncology for Somatic NGS	Catalan Institute of Oncology (ICO) - Hospitalet Branch
SPAIN	ESMTB04	Multi-institutional	Comité molecular de Salamanca-Zamora-Avila	Complejo Asistencial de Zamora
SPAIN	ESMTB07	Local	MOlecular Tumor Board	Hospital Clinico de Santiago de Universitario

Figure 1: List of MTBs for which patient information is provided. For each MTB, the country, assigned MTB code, MTB name, geographical scope, and participating institutions are included.

The estimated percentages of patient outcomes were categorized across the following ranges: 0–20%, 21–40%, 41–60%, 61–80%, and 81–100%.

In 30.8% of MTBs, the estimated proportion of **discussed patients receiving an MTB treatment recommendation** falls within the 21–40% range, while 23.1% reported proportions within the 41–60% range. The remaining MTBs report results evenly distributed across the other ranges, with 15% in each (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Percentage of patients receiving a MTB treatment recommendation across countries and MTBs

The estimates of patients receiving an MTB recommendation are more variable for **MTB recommendations specifically based on the presence of a molecular alteration**: 31% of MTBs place this proportion in the 0–20% range of patients discussed, 38% in the 21–40% range, and 23% in the 41–60% range. Notably, the national Belgian MTB estimates this figure to fall within the 61–80% range (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Percentage of patients receiving a MTB treatment recommendation specifically based on the presence of a molecular alteration across countries and MTBs

Figure 4 highlights two distinct approaches that MTBs may adopt in their clinical decision-making processes. i) MTBs based mainly on genetic alterations; ii) MTBs more broadly focused on providing treatment recommendations that are not necessarily tied to the presence of a molecular alteration.

Figure 4: The percentage of patients receiving an MTB treatment recommendation, or an MTB recommendation specifically based on the presence of a molecular alteration, is provided for each MTB.

Overall, 67% of MTBs refer 0–20% of the patients they discuss to **clinical trials**. Similarly, 67% of MTBs direct 0–20% of patients toward **off-label drug use**. For Standard-of-Care (SoC) treatment recommendations, results vary across MTBs: 54% estimate that 0–20% of their discussed patients receive such recommendations, 23% estimate this proportion to be 21–40%, and another 23% estimate it to be 41–60%.

Figure 5: The percentage of patients receiving a standard-of-care, clinical trial or off-label drug recommendation is provided for each MTB.

MTBs based mainly on genetic alterations focus primarily on providing treatment recommendations based on genetic or molecular alterations identified in a patient’s tumor, while other MTBs are more broadly focused on providing treatment recommendations that are not necessarily tied to the presence of a molecular alteration, by including other diagnostic factors such as pathological evaluation or clinical context: These MTBs may be more involved in determining or refining the

diagnosis, especially in complex or rare cases, where molecular information might not be available or relevant.

A significant proportion of both profiles of MTBs provide recommendations for discussed patients in lower ranges (0–20% or 21–40%), indicating a relatively modest impact on patient management. This may reflect limitations in available resources, trial accessibility, or patient eligibility.

With 67% of MTBs estimating that only 0–20% of patients receive recommendations for clinical trials or off-label drug use, there appears to be a significant gap in leveraging these options. This might indicate barriers such as limited trial availability, restrictive eligibility criteria, or lack of funding for off-label treatments. These numbers are in line with existing literature^{1–3}.

SoC recommendations are also predominantly concentrated in the 0–20% range (54%), some MTBs report higher proportions of patients with SoC recommendations. This could indicate that MTBs focus more on innovative or investigational approaches rather than routine care, or that SoC recommendations are made outside the MTB setting.

II. ICO survey results

An electronic survey (**Annex II**) was carried out by ICO and distributed by e-mail in collaboration with the Spanish Group of Lung Cancer (GECP) cooperative group. A total of 44 participants completed the survey, the majority of whom were medical oncologists (93.2%) and males (69%). The median age of the respondents was 47 years, with greater representation from regions such as Madrid, Catalunya and Andalusia.

The majority of participants (79.5%) reported having access to NGS in clinical practice. Among those with access, 45.5% used NGS exclusively for solid tumors, while 38.6% applied it to both solid tumors and liquid biopsies. Additionally, most participants with NGS access (69.4%) regularly participated in the Molecular Tumor Board, with 52.7% indicated that they only discussed selected cases.

The average turn-around-time (TAT) from NGS request to NGS report was estimated to 16 days, with the majority of participants (52.7%) not satisfied with the duration. Routine NGS testing in clinical practice have been implemented in 69.4% of participating centers. NGS reports are uploaded in the medical records in 91.6% of cases, while 54.5% of participants reported storing molecular and clinicopathological data in an electronic database. However, a significant proportion of respondents (52.3%) were unable to estimate the proportion of patients in whom an actionable alteration was detected.

Although the survey did not include a specific question to estimate the number of patients directed by the MTB towards personalized medicine, it was noteworthy that 47.7% of respondents considered that patients were not receiving therapies recommended by MTBs. The most commonly cited barrier to targeted therapy was limited access to specific treatments.

III. Literature review

The frequency of patients receiving treatment recommendations from an MTB varies widely across the analyzed studies, ranging from 6% to 65% (refer to the table below).

Institution	Country	Study or MTB	% of total patients treated with matched therapy
Institut Curie, Gustave Roussy and others	France	SAFIR02-BREAST and SAFIR-PI3K ^{4,5}	65%
Institut Curie	France	SHIVA01 ⁶	14%
DKFZ	Germany	CATCH	50%
Gustave Roussy	France	PRISM ⁷	7%
Léon Bérard Cancer center and others	France	ProfiLER ⁸	6%
Princess Margaret Cancer center	Canada	IMPACT/COMPACT ⁹	15%
CRUK Manchester, Christie	UK	TARGET ¹⁰	11%
Various institutions	International	WINTHER ¹¹	NA
ASCO	USA	TAPUR ¹²	NA
Zurich University and others	Switzerland	TuPro ¹³	NA
Institut Curie	France	Institutional MTB ¹	8%
Mayo Clinic	USA	Center for Individualized Medicine MTB ¹⁴	20%
UCSD Moores Cancer center	USA	San Diego Moores Cancer Center MTB ¹⁵	40%
University of Wisconsin, William S. Middleton VA Medical Center, Gundersen Health System, Aurora Health Care and Green Bay oncology	USA	Regional MTB ¹⁶	11%
Various institutions from Kentucky, Illinois, Wisconsin	USA	Regional MTB ¹⁷	14%

Figure 6: Overview of clinical studies or MTBs from the literature. Each entry includes the institution, country, study name or MTB scope, and the percentage of patients treated with matched therapy if available.

These studies enrolled different tumor types, employed different genomic or transcriptomic testing platforms and were designed independently, making indirect comparisons challenging. The differences in the percentage of total patients treated with matched therapies across the studies and MTBs listed in the table can however be explained by several contributing factors.

One significant factor is the characteristics of the patient population. Trials or MTBs with strict inclusion criteria, such as requiring an ECOG (Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group) performance status of less than 2, tend to select patients in better overall health, leading to higher matched therapy rates. On the other hand, real-world MTBs often handle patients with poorer performance status, which lowers their chances of receiving matched therapies.

Another key factor is the distinction between study design and real-world practice. Clinical trials such as SAFIR02-BREAST and CATCH are often structured to evaluate specific matched therapies, with protocols in place to ensure access to these treatments, resulting in higher matched therapy

rates. Conversely, institutional or regional MTBs typically operate in real-world settings where logistical, financial, or regulatory barriers can limit access to matched therapies. This disparity is evident in the lower percentages observed in MTBs like those at Institut Curie or regional MTBs.

Access to targeted therapies also plays a critical role. Institutions in countries with better access to targeted therapies—whether through national health programs or pharmaceutical partnerships—are likely to report higher matched therapy rates. Conversely, limited availability of drugs in some regions directly reduces the proportion of patients receiving matched therapies. Clinical trial enrollment can mitigate this issue to some extent. For example, studies such as SAFIRO2-BREAST and CATCH integrate clinical trial enrollment into their protocols, ensuring that patients with actionable alterations have access to experimental therapies, thereby improving match rates.

The level of molecular profiling is an additional influencing factor. The extent of molecular profiling available at different institutions significantly impacts outcomes. Institutions using comprehensive genomic profiling can identify more actionable alterations compared to those with narrower profiling approaches. Moreover, delays in molecular profiling or treatment initiation can limit access to matched therapies, particularly for patients with aggressive or rapidly progressing cancers.

The focus of the study or MTB is another consideration. Studies targeting specific molecular pathways, such as PI3K in SAFIR-PI3K, tend to achieve higher matched therapy rates because they are designed to identify and treat patients with these particular alterations. In contrast, general MTBs without a specific therapeutic focus may report lower matched therapy rates due to a broader and less selective patient population.

Finally, institutional experience and resources contribute to the observed differences. Institutions with dedicated MTBs or significant experience in molecular oncology are better equipped to integrate profiling and therapy. Variations in funding, technology, and personnel across institutions further contribute to discrepancies in matched therapy rates.

Conclusion and discussion

Data collected from the literature and from surveys conducted by the CanHeal consortium highlights several critical factors influencing the variability in the percentage of patients oriented towards personalised medicine.

Analysis of the surveys reveals that a significant proportion of MTBs provide treatment recommendations for a relatively small percentage of patients.

As part of the collaborative CanHeal survey, among the 13 MTBs reporting on patient orientation to personalized treatment, only 0-20% of patients are referred to clinical trials or off-label drug use. This highlights challenges in accessing these treatment options, such as restrictive eligibility criteria, limited availability, and funding constraints. Consequently, the influence of MTBs on patient management appears to be somewhat limited.

Furthermore, a notable proportion of MTBs provide SoC recommendations for a small percentage of patients (0-20%). This may suggest that MTBs focus more on innovative or investigational therapies. The concept of tumor-agnostic approaches, where therapy recommendations are based on molecular alterations rather than tumor histology aligns with the increasing shift toward personalized medicine and molecular profiling in oncology.

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In the context of the ICO survey, a majority of participants reported having access to NGS in clinical practice, with most using it for solid tumors. However, 47.7% of respondents estimated that patients were not receiving the therapies recommended by the MTBs. Limited access to specific treatments was the most commonly cited barrier to targeted therapy.

Literature reviewed in this Deliverable further reinforces the idea that several factors contribute to the variation in matched therapy rates. These include patient population characteristics, study design, access to targeted therapies, molecular profiling, and institutional experience. Studies with strict inclusion criteria tend to show higher matched therapy rates. Additionally, institutions with better access to targeted therapies and those using comprehensive molecular profiling approaches are more likely to report higher success in identifying actionable alterations.

In conclusion, the differences in matched therapy rates across studies and MTBs reflect a complex interplay of factors, including patient selection, study design, access to therapies, and institutional resources. While clinical trials and specialized MTBs may offer higher matched therapy rates, real-world MTBs face numerous barriers that limit their impact. Low matched therapy rate could be explained by the patient population that is referred in routine, usually heavily pre-treated. Access to clinical trials is limited due to inclusion criteria that make difficult for patients with recurrent and/or metastatic cancers in poor general condition to be referred for clinical trial inclusion. This suggests a possible misalignment between MTB practices and patients' ability to access testing and therapies, emphasizing a key area for improvement.

Overcoming these challenges—particularly by enhancing access to molecular profiling and targeted therapies—is crucial for improving the effectiveness of MTBs and advancing personalized cancer care. Meanwhile, reporting on the current number of patients directed toward personalized treatment establishes a strong foundation for engaging in productive discussions with providers, stakeholders, health authorities, policymakers, and other key parties. These efforts will promote knowledge exchange, foster collaboration, and ensure alignment on shared goals, such as optimizing precision medicine implementation, driving innovation, and tackling public health challenges.

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ANNEX I - Survey report on next generation sequencing, Molecular Tumour Board and oncology Decision Support Tool practices in Europe: Molecular Tumour Board excerpt

ANNEX II - Electronic survey carried out by ICO between November and December 2024

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ANNEX I: SURVEY REPORT ON NEXT GENERATION SEQUENCING, MOLECULAR TUMOUR BOARD AND ONCOLOGY DECISION SUPPORT TOOL PRACTICES IN EUROPE: MOLECULAR TUMOUR BOARD EXCERPT

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Authors	
Name	Partner
Nancy Frédérickx	Sciensano - Cancer-Centre
Els Van Valckenborgh	Sciensano - Cancer-Centre
Julie Maetens	Sciensano - Cancer-Centre
Zeina Chamoun-Morel	Institut Curie
Célia Dupain	Institut Curie

Contributors	
Name	Partner

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ABBREVIATIONS

MTB	Molecular Tumor Board
NGS	Next-Generation Sequencing
SoC	Standard-of-care
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation

INTRODUCTION AND AIMS

CAN.HEAL (<https://canheal.eu/>) aims to improve access of individuals to prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of cancer through personalised medicine, by upscaling available innovation with the focus on applying 'Next Generation Sequencing (NGS)' technology and identifying implementation paths. To get an overview of the European landscape, a survey across Europe was disseminated through the CAN.HEAL consortium.

This report highlights the results collected through the survey that map the current practices in European countries on:

- i) NGS 'wet lab' and 'dry lab',
- ii) Molecular tumour board (MTB),
- iii) oncology Decision support tool (oncDST) and
- iv) Regulatory, economic and health care policy aspects of NGS

Our analysis results in identifying gaps and challenges that need to be addressed by healthcare providers and policymakers.

METHODOLOGY

The survey was developed through extensive collaboration among WP8 (Diagnosis and Treatment via MTB), WP9 (Treatment and Follow-up), and WP10 (oncology Decision Support Tools, oncDSTs). To facilitate participants' engagement, the survey was divided into 4 sections: as outlined in the introduction. This structure ensured that institutional coordinators had access to the complete survey, while other participants were directed to specific sections relevant to their expertise, based on their responses to specific questions.

Set up as a Google Form, the survey was initially disseminated via email to the Can.Heal consortium. Members were then encouraged to share the survey within their relevant networks. This approach aimed to reach a broad audience across Europe, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the current European landscape of genomics application in cancer diagnostics and treatment.

After four months, the data collected via the Google Form analyzed using Excel. Given the large volume of information, the analysis was distributed among the various WPs based on their specific areas of focus and expertise. The divisions were as follows: NGS 'wet lab' and 'dry lab' sections was analyzed by WP9.

- i) MTB section was analyzed by WP8.
- ii) DST section was analyzed by WP10.
- iii) Regulatory, economic, and healthcare policy aspects of NGS section was analyzed by WP9 and WP3.

Following the preliminary analysis, meetings were organized to consolidate the findings and formulate the final conclusions.

To ensure a clear overview of the data, each institute contributor was assigned a unique code. This allowed for parallel analysis of responses from the same institute and prevented duplicate answers from being included in the final results.

RESULTS

1. GENERAL INFORMATION

The survey achieved significant success with 116 responses from across Europe. This included participants from 14 EU member countries and 3 non-EU countries: Serbia, Norway, and England (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Participating countries across Europe

Among the 116 participants, the highest number of responses came from Spain with 34 participants, followed by Belgium with 17 participants, and France and Italy with 16 participants each. These figures represent contributions from 29 different institutions in Spain, 10 in Belgium, 15 in France, and 12 in Italy. Figure 2 provides an overview of the geographic distribution of the 116 participants. Annex 1 lists the institutes that participated in the survey for each country along with their assigned codes, facilitating the interpretation of this report.

Countries	Number of participants	Number of Institutions
Spain	34	30
Belgium	17	10
France	16	15
Italy	16	12
Germany	10	07
Netherlands	5	04
Other	5	03
Poland	4	04
Greece	3	03
Slovenia	3	01
Estonia	2	01
Czech Republic	1	01
Denmark	1	01
Malta	1	01
Portugal	1	01

Figure 2: Number of participants and institutions within a country.

The majority of participants holds role as either molecular biologists involved in diagnostics, clinicians or specialists in laboratory medicine including clinical pathologists, clinical geneticists and clinical biologists.

A total of 41 participants, serving as institutional MTB coordinators completed the entire survey, while 75 others filled sections related to their specific areas of expertise.

2. MOLECULAR TUMOR BOARD

The survey included 45 questions designed to map the current practices of MTBs organization across the EU. These questions addressed various aspects of MTBs such as the logistical organization (format and composition), geographical scope (local, multi-institutional, national, or international), the patient populations discussed (adult or paediatric), the types of cancers addressed (localization, stage etc.), the recommendations done after discussing a case and follow-up procedures. Out of the 116 respondents, 75 (65%) reported participation in one or more MTBs.

As part of the methodology, when multiple entries referred to the same MTB, only one response was selected to avoid redundancy, prioritizing input from the MTB coordinator whenever possible. For example, although information on the National Belgian MTB BALLETT was provided by 11 respondents from 7 different institutions in Belgium, only the coordinator's answer was retained.

In total, 54 unique MTBs were identified (see Figure 3 for their distribution across Europe by cities and countries).

Figure 3: Map of MTBs distribution in Europe

Each MTB was given a unique code beginning with the two-letter country code, enabling identification and comparison of results.

Among 54 MTBs, detailed information was available for 49 MTBs, provided by 17 MTB coordinators and 32 MTB participants knowledgeable about their organizational aspects (listed in Annex 2). The

remaining 5 MTBs were included by participants who were less familiar with their organizational aspects and therefore could not fill in the related MTB section.

The analysis outlined in the following sections integrates the detailed responses from the 49 MTBs. It is important to note that respondents provided input based on their individual expertise and experience. Any discrepancies in responses related to the same MTB were resolved by contacting the respondents via email for clarification. Additionally, according to the survey setting, each respondent provided information for only one MTB, specifically the most comprehensive MTB they participated in. For instance, a respondent involved in both a local and a national MTB would complete the survey based on their participation in the national MTB. Therefore, the number of MTBs might be underestimated in this survey.

2.1 Organizational aspects of the MTBs

2.1.1 Geographical scope

Figure 4 illustrates the distribution of MTBs, categorized as operating at a local, multi-institutional, or national level.

Figure 4: organizational levels of MTBs across countries

2.1.2 Format and frequency

Seventy-nine percent of MTBs are conducted either virtually or in a hybrid format, which can contribute to save time and allows extra-institutional experts consultations. Most MTBs follow a regular schedule, with 35% meeting weekly, 44% biweekly, and 12% monthly, suggesting a strong demand for MTBs

Most of the MTBs (80%) are part of routine clinical practice, while 10% are organized as part of a real-world clinical project, and 6% are linked to a specific clinical study.

2.1.3 MTB Composition

MTBs bring together a diverse range of multidisciplinary specialists to enable comprehensive discussions. In 50% of the reported MTBs, at least six distinct professional roles are involved, underscoring the collaborative and multifaceted nature of these meetings.

A core MTB group typically consists of one or more medical oncologists (93%), molecular biologists (88%), and specialists in laboratory medicine (82%), such as clinical pathologists, biologists, and chemists. Clinical geneticists, hematologists, and bioinformaticians are involved in approximately 50% of MTBs. Data managers, research study nurses, and biostatisticians participate less frequently (18%-8

12%). Additional professionals may complement the core group, varying by institutions or the nature of the cases discussed in the specific MTB (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Distribution of expertise participating in MTBs

The key experts participating in various MTBs include oncologists, molecular biologists, and laboratory medicine specialists. These findings are consistent with those reported in Can.Heal Deliverable D8.1, with the notable exception of bioinformaticians, whose participation was reported in 40.8% of survey responses compared to 15% in D8.1.

It is also unclear whether MTBs consistently include coordination teams, as this aspect was not clearly addressed in the survey design. However, according to D8.1; a coordination team was part of 64% of MTBs.

This aligns with the recommendations for MTB composition outlined in the MTB guidelines provided in Can.Heal Deliverable D8.3 (Standardised guidelines for molecular interpretation).

The fact that the vast majority of MTBs operate within routine practice demonstrates their acceptance as a standard approach in oncology. This reflects the increasing reliance on multidisciplinary collaboration for personalized treatment planning and decision-making. Overall, the data demonstrates the growing institutionalization of MTBs in oncology.

2.2 MTB preparation

In most MTBs, patients can be referred by various specialists including their treating physician (in 98 % of all MTBs) by a specialist in laboratory medicine (37.5% of all MTBs) or to a lesser extent by a clinical geneticist. Case preparation is typically handled by the treating physician, individual specialists, or a dedicated MTB coordinator. Notably, 80% of MTBs have a designated coordinator, emphasizing their crucial role in organizing and streamlining the discussion process.

2.2.1 Patients discussed:

Among the MTBs described, 80% focus on adult patients, 18% encompass both adult and pediatric patients, and only 2% are exclusively dedicated to the pediatric population, indicating a significant underrepresentation of pediatric MTBs in the survey responses (Figure 6)

Interestingly, while pediatric MTBs are less frequently represented in the survey, they are more often organized at a national or multi-institutional level (n=5/10; 50%).

Figure 6: Patient populations discussed across MTBs

The number of patients discussed annually by MTBs varies across different ranges: 18% of MTBs discuss 0–50 patients, 26.5% discuss 50–100 patients, 22.4% handle 100–300 patients, 24.5% review 300–500 patients, and 8.2% discuss 500–1,000 patients (Figure 7).

The majority of MTBs discuss between 50 and 500 patients annually. A smaller proportion manage either a low (0-50%), 18%) or high (500-1000 patients, 8,2%) patient volume

Lower patient volume are discussed by local MTBs, except for ESMT16 (multi-institutional MTB of the San Carlos hospital) and EEMTB01 (National MTB of Estonia).

A higher annual patient volume is associated with the national MTB in Norway, as well as two local MTBs and one multi-institutional MTB in Spain.

Figure 7: Number of patients discussed per year across MTBs

Regarding the types of cancers discussed, 41% of MTBs adopt a tumor-agnostic approach, addressing all types of solid tumors. A further 24% are dedicated to specific solid tumor types, while 27% discuss both solid tumors and hematological neoplasms. Only 8% are exclusively focused on hematological neoplasms. (Figure 8)

Figure 8: Cancer types discussed across MTBs

Among the MTBs described, 53% discuss patients across all stages of cancer, including non-metastatic settings such as neoadjuvant treatment planning. A further 25% are focused on refractory diseases where standard-of-care treatments have been exhausted. 12% of MTBs address cases from progression beyond first-line treatment and later stages, and 10% are dedicated to first-line systemic treatment decisions in metastatic settings and subsequent stages (Figure 9)

Figure 9: Stages of disease discussed across MTBs

This distribution illustrates the broad scope of MTBs, with a majority addressing a comprehensive range of cancer stages, while others specialize in more advanced or complex scenarios. One limitation of the survey is the underrepresentation of pediatric and hematologic MTBs. Pediatric MTBs are already well organized at multi-institutional and international levels, serving as exemplary models of collaboration and organization. It will be important in the future to draw inspiration from their frameworks to further improve MTB practices. Interestingly, 41% of MTBs reported adopting a tumor-agnostic (i.e. histology-independent) approach, accommodating all solid tumors. As outlined in the MTB recommendation from Can.Heal D8.3, many actionable alterations discussed in MTBs have approved drugs for certain indications but are still in clinical development for others. Expanding these indications often involves testing across different tumor types or molecular subtypes. MTB profiling is often referred to as "agnostic," since therapy recommendations are based on molecular alteration rather than tumor histology.

2.2.2 Integration and Utilization of NGS Testing in MTB Workflows

In most MTBs (73%), NGS is initiated by the treating physician or pathologist prior to the MTB meeting, indicating a proactive approach to ensure that molecular data is available to inform discussions and decisions during MTB sessions. This practice also suggests that the integration of NGS into routine oncology workflows has become commonplace, especially for complex cases where MTBs are convened.

Conversely, in 25% of cases, NGS testing is prescribed by the MTB itself, streamlining the diagnostic process. This approach might reflect situations where the initial molecular workup is deemed insufficient,

requiring more comprehensive or specific NGS assays. It also highlights the role of MTBs in guiding additional diagnostic efforts, especially in challenging or refractory cases where deeper molecular insights are necessary .

The distribution of NGS techniques highlights the diversity of molecular diagnostics utilized in cancer care (Figure 10):

- Targeted DNA sequencing + RNA sequencing (61%) and targeted DNA sequencing only (57%) dominate as the most frequently prescribed assays. These methods are well-suited for identifying actionable mutations and alterations in both the DNA and RNA landscapes, such as single-nucleotide variants, gene fusions, and expression changes.
- Comprehensive genomic profiling (CGP), including genome-wide biomarkers, is prescribed in 51% of cases, reflecting the increasing ability to assess broader genomic contexts, such as tumor mutational burden (TMB) or microsatellite instability (MSI), in therapeutic decision-making.
- Total RNA sequencing, whole-exome sequencing (WES), whole-genome sequencing (WGS), and methylomics are used to a lesser extent. These more expansive and complex techniques may be reserved for select cases requiring deeper exploration of molecular mechanisms, and be only accessible to specific countries for which regional or national initiatives including testing reimbursement are provided (see Can.Heal Deliverable D8.2).

Figure 10: Distribution of NGS assays across MTBs

MTBs might employ various NGS techniques tailored to the specific requirements of each case, as depicted in Figure 11.

Figure 11: NGS techniques utilized per MTB across countries

Targeted DNA and RNA sequencing dominate as the most used techniques, while comprehensive genomic profiling is increasingly employed for broader genomic insights. More complex approaches, like WES, WGS, and methylomics, are less common and often limited to specific contexts with dedicated initiatives or reimbursement programs. As outlined in Can.Heal Deliberable 8.2, only 6 out of 9 national initiatives included WES or WGS analyses.

2.2.3 Distribution of Laboratory settings for NGS testing in MTBs

The distribution of laboratory settings for NGS testing in the context of MTBs offers valuable insights into logistical practices and resource utilization in molecular oncology (Figure 12):

- Local Hospital Laboratories (62%): The majority of NGS testing is performed in local hospital laboratories, likely due to the convenience, quick turnaround times, and the ability to integrate results seamlessly into the patient’s clinical care. This reflects the increasing accessibility of NGS technology at the institutional level and suggests that many hospitals have invested in in-house capabilities to support personalized oncology.

- Regional or National Reference Laboratories (22%): These laboratories play a significant role, especially in cases where more specialized or comprehensive testing is required. MTBs often rely on these centralized facilities for their expertise, standardization, and advanced resources that may not be available at the local level.

- External Hospital or Commercial Laboratories (8%): Testing done in these settings is less common, possibly due to logistical challenges, cost considerations, or institutional preferences for in-house or trusted regional laboratories. However, commercial laboratories can provide access to cutting-edge testing platforms and broader assay panels, especially for rare or complex cases.

- Use of Multiple Laboratories: Some MTBs utilize multiple laboratories (local, regional, or commercial) depending on the specific needs of a case. This flexibility allows MTBs to tailor the choice of laboratory based on the type of NGS test required, turnaround time, cost, or specific expertise offered by different facilities.

The current distribution of laboratory settings reflects a tiered approach to NGS testing, where local laboratories, when available, handle the bulk of cases, while regional and commercial facilities provide supplementary support for more complex needs.

Figure 12: Distribution of laboratory settings for NGS testing across MTBs

2.2.4 Patient consent

The data on how patients are informed about NGS testing reveals critical insights into consent practices and patient engagement in the molecular oncology workflow.

The following patient Consent Practices are reported among the participants:

Written Consent (74%)

The majority of cases involve written consent, which is the gold standard for ensuring that patients are adequately informed about the testing process and its implications.

Advantages: Written consent provides a formal, documented process that protects both patients and providers. It ensures clarity about the purpose, scope, and potential outcomes of the testing, as well as privacy and data-sharing considerations.

Challenges: The effectiveness of written consent depends on the patient's comprehension of the information provided, which can vary based on literacy, medical knowledge, and the complexity of the information.

Oral Consent (10%)

Oral consent is used in a minority of cases, likely for situations where formal documentation is less practical or where testing is integrated into routine clinical workflows.

Advantages: Oral consent may streamline the process in urgent situations or when NGS is an anticipated part of care.

Challenges: It lacks the documentation and legal protections of written consent, which may lead to misunderstandings or disputes about whether patients were adequately informed.

No Consent (16%)

A significant minority of cases proceed without informing patients about NGS testing. This might raise ethical concerns, as patients may be unaware of how their genetic data is being used, stored, or shared. It may also conflict with guidelines and legal requirements in many jurisdictions, which emphasize the importance of informed consent in genomic testing.

Potential Justifications: In some healthcare settings, testing may be integrated into standard care protocols, with assumptions that consent is implicit.

While the high prevalence of written consent reflects a commitment to patient-centered care, the existence of cases with no consent is a concerning gap. Addressing this issue through improved standardization, education, and oversight is essential to ensure that NGS testing aligns with ethical principles, patient autonomy, and regulatory standards. Obtaining written patients consent for NGS testing is also crucial to ensure that their data can be ethically reused for research purposes, especially in Europe, where GDPR regulations impose strict requirements on data protection and consent management.

2.3 Results reporting

The methods used to communicate NGS results and MTB recommendations to treating physicians highlight the diversity of practices and the varying levels of digital infrastructure in healthcare systems (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Distribution of results' communication methods across MTBs

Electronic Health Records (EHRs) – 45%

EHRs are the most common means of communication, likely due to their integration into hospital systems and routine workflows.

Advantages: EHRs facilitate seamless access to NGS results and MTB recommendations alongside other patient data. They also ensure that information is securely stored and readily accessible for future reference.

Challenges: Not all EHR systems are optimized for handling complex genomic data, potentially limiting the interpretability of results. Variability in EHR capabilities across institutions can hinder standardization.

Email – 23%

Email remains a widely used method, likely for its speed and simplicity.

Advantages: it enables direct and quick communication, especially for urgent cases. It allows for the attachment of detailed reports and supplementary materials.

Challenges: there might be security concerns regarding the transmission of sensitive patient data. It might be coupled to a lack of integration with other clinical systems, requiring physicians to manually input or reference information.

Paper Reports – 15%

Paper reports are less commonly used, reflecting the shift toward digital methods.

Advantages: it provides a tangible, portable record for physicians who may prefer non-digital documentation.

Challenges: it is slower and less efficient compared to digital methods, and there is a risk of loss or misplacement, and difficulty in integrating with EHR systems.

Dedicated Online MTB Portals – 9%

Specialized MTB portals are used in a minority of cases, likely reflecting the uneven availability of such platforms.

Advantages: it is tailored to display detailed genomic results, recommendations, and decision-making support tools. It facilitates collaboration and communication among MTB members and treating physicians.

Challenges: it requires significant investment in infrastructure and training, and its adoption may be limited by interoperability issues with existing clinical systems.

National or Regional Health Record Hubs – 5%

This is the least common method, used in only a small percentage of cases.

Advantages: centralized systems might improve accessibility and standardization across institutions.

Challenges: it might be limited by geographic or jurisdictional constraints, and its implementation might be resource-intensive and may face political and logistical barriers.

The current communication practices for NGS results and MTB recommendations reflect a healthcare landscape transitioning toward digital solutions, albeit with gaps in standardization and accessibility. Expanding the use of integrated, secure, and user-friendly systems like EHRs and dedicated MTB portals will enhance the efficiency, security, and interpretability of these critical data exchanges.

2.4 Germline Data Discussion and Follow-up in MTBs

The majority of MTBs (86%) discuss and report germline data, with 78% of these subsequently referring patients for genetic counseling. However, in 14% of MTBs, germline data are not addressed (Figure 14).

Follow-up on germline findings occurs in 83% of MTBs. Of these, 54% conduct follow-ups through case-by-case discussions within the MTB, while 29% follow a systematic approach based on expert guidelines, such as those from ESMO. However, in 17% of MTBs, germline findings are not followed up.

The identification of germline mutations following NGS analyses requires a multidisciplinary approach, with genetic counseling as a cornerstone. Distinguishing between somatic and germline mutations can be complex, often requiring parallel testing of non-tumor tissue (e.g., blood or saliva). Variants of Uncertain Significance (VUS) add to the complexity, as MTBs must decide how to interpret these findings and whether additional testing or surveillance is warranted.

By addressing both therapeutic and familial implications, MTBs can provide recommendations that extends beyond the immediate cancer treatment to long-term risk management and familial health. Genetic counseling is of utmost important in germline cases, providing education to help patients understand the implications of germline mutations for themselves and their families. Additionally, testing for at-risk family members often require expert guidance.

Figure 14: Germline data discussion across MTBs

2.5 MTBs recommendations

2.5.1 Types of treatment recommendations

MTBs make a variety of recommendations (Figure 15), including referrals to clinical trials (96%), suggestions for standard-of-care treatments (79%), proposals for off-label drug use (75.5%), or

guidance toward medical need or compassionate use programs (75.5%). In many cases, MTBs may provide multiple recommendations, tailored to the specifics of each patient's situation.

Figure 15: types of treatment recommendations across MTBs

2.5.2 Diagnostic recommendations

The majority of MTBs (67%) provide diagnostic recommendations to some extent, with tentative diagnoses sometimes being revised following MTB discussions. In 16% of MTBs, diagnostic recommendations are made routinely, whereas 10% of MTBs do not provide any diagnostic recommendations.

2.6 MTBs recommendations statistics

Outcome and statistics were provided for 13 MTBs out of 49. The low response rate may stem from a lack of information among respondents regarding their MTB's statistical outcomes, or the absence of follow-up data collection. Alternatively, respondents may have been restricted from sharing data due to confidentiality concerns or institutional policies.

The estimated percentage of patients' outcomes was tracked across the ranges of 0–20%, 21–40%, 41–60%, 61–80%, and 81–100% (Figure 16)

Figure 16: percentage of patients receiving a MTB treatments recommendation

In 38% of MTBs, the estimated proportion of discussed patients **receiving an MTB treatment recommendation** falls within the 21–40% range. The remaining MTBs report results evenly distributed across the other ranges, with 15% in each.

For **MTB recommendations specifically based on the presence of a molecular alteration**, the estimates are more variable: 31% of MTBs place this proportion in the 0–20% range of patients discussed, 38% in the 21–40% range, and 23% in the 41–60% range. Notably, the national Belgian MTB estimates this figure to fall within the 61–80% range.

62% of MTBs refer 0–20% of the patients they discuss to clinical trials. Similarly, 62% of MTBs direct 0–20% of patients toward off-label drug use. For **standard-of-care (SoC) treatment** recommendations, results vary across MTBs: 54% estimate that 0–20% of their discussed patients receive such recommendations, 23% estimate this proportion to be 21–40%, and another 23% estimate it to be 41–60%.

The results shows that a significant proportion of MTBs provide recommendations for discussed patients in lower ranges (0–20% or 21–40%), indicating a relatively modest impact on patient management. This may reflect limitations in available resources, trial accessibility, or patient eligibility.

With 67% of MTBs estimating that only 0–20% of patients receive recommendations for clinical trials or off-label drug use, there appears to be a significant gap in leveraging these options. This might indicate barriers such as limited trial availability, restrictive eligibility criteria, or lack of funding for off-label treatments. These numbers are in line with existing literature^{1–3}.

SoC recommendations are also largely concentrated in the 0–20% range (54%), even though a few MTBs report higher proportions of patients with SoC recommendations. This could indicate that MTBs focus more on innovative or investigational approaches rather than routine care, or that standard-of-care recommendations are made outside the MTB setting.

2.7 MTBs follow-up

Follow-up data are collected and statistically analyzed for 29 MTBs out of a total of 49 (59%, compared to 91% in Can.Heal Deliverable 8.1). However, information was available for only 9 MTBs, as 66% of respondents for the 29 MTBs were either unaware of the outcomes or restricted from sharing the results.

The limited awareness or restrictions on sharing outcomes underlines a significant gap in data availability, which may limit comprehensive analysis of MTBs performance.

Estimates for patients **receiving MTB-recommended treatment** show significant variability.

Among the 9 MTBs, 3 report proportions of patients in the 21–40% range, another 3 in the 41–60% range, while the remaining 3 are evenly distributed across the 0–20%, 61–80%, and 81–100% ranges. This variability may reflect differences in implementation strategies, patient demographics, or institutional resources.

Notably, reasons for not following MTB treatment recommendations are monitored and recorded in only 4 MTBs out of 9.

Similarly, the estimated mean delay between an MTB recommendation and the initiation of treatment or inclusion in a clinical trial also showed considerable variation. Among the 9 MTBs, 4 reported an estimated delay of 5–10 calendar days, 2 reported 11–20 calendar days, 2 reported delays exceeding 20 calendar days, and 1 estimated a delay of less than 5 calendar days.

The data highlights substantial variability in both the proportion of patients receiving MTB-recommended treatment and the delay in treatment initiation or clinical trial inclusion. However, potential biases in understanding the survey question: "What is the percentage of patients receiving the MTB recommended treatment?" should be noted. Respondents might interpret this

as referring either to the total patient population or only to the subset of patients for whom the MTB provided a recommendation. This variation in interpretation changes the denominator and therefore the percentage, making it challenging to accurately interpret the results.

The outcomes of patients receiving MTB-recommended treatment are documented in 67% of MTBs. Among these, half systematically register the outcomes, while the other half do so selectively for certain cases. In the remaining third of MTBs, patient outcomes for MTB-recommended treatment are not documented at all.

Within MTBs that document outcomes, inconsistencies are evident, with half lacking a systematic approach. Identifying the criteria for selective record keeping could provide valuable insights. The absence of documentation in a third of MTBs creates significant data gaps that could hinder any assessment of treatment efficacy and the overall value of MTB recommendations. Notably, few studies in the literature have evaluated the impact of MTBs, and they report a low proportion of patients receiving matched therapies (ranging from 5% to 43%)^{1,4–10}. These numbers may increase over time, as more matched therapy options become available in recent studies.

These observations align with recommendations outlined in Can.Heal D8.3 (Standardised guidelines for molecular interpretation), emphasizing the need for indicators to be made for each patient to monitor MTB function. To enhance data sharing and enable broader analysis, it is crucial to adopt standardized metrics for MTB reporting, which will require significant efforts in data formatting and analysis.

2.8 Respondents' Insights on Barriers to Patient Enrollment in MTB-Recommended Clinical Trials

Respondents were asked to share their opinions on the reasons behind patients' lack of enrollment in MTB-recommended clinical trials, drawing either from data monitoring or their personal experience.

Figure 17 displays the results, with participants having the option to specify up to two reasons.

Figure 17: Factors contributing to patients' lack of enrollment in MTB recommended clinical trials.

Over 30% of responses identified three primary reasons for patients lack of enrollment in clinical trials after an MTB recommendation: patient deterioration or death (36.7%), cohort closure (32.7%) and geographical distance from trial site (30.6%).

Additionally, 26.5% of the responses indicated that the possibility of clinical trial enrolment was reserved as a future option.

Other reasons included the lack of local support for the treating physician (14.3%) and patient-dependent factors. Among these, 22.4% cited comorbidities as a barrier to enrollment, while 4.1% reported lack of patient interest.

The percentage of patients who actually receive treatment following MTB discussions remains low. To minimize delays in obtaining molecular results that often align with patient health deterioration, the D8.3 guidelines recommend initiating testing as soon as disease progression is detected. Additionally, clinical trials in Europe need to adapt to be more accessible to patients, by ensuring the availability of cohorts and providing greater support to local physicians.

2.9 Respondents' Perspectives on the Role and Challenges of MTB Meetings

Questions were designed to gather personal insights on the effectiveness and challenges of MTB meetings. Respondents were asked to evaluate the importance of MTB meetings in patient management decision-making, the role of molecular findings in refining diagnoses, and the educational benefits derived from discussing individual cases that may assist other patients. Additionally, the time-consuming nature of MTB meetings and their potential delays in treatment initiation were addressed. Lastly, the difficulty of organizing MTB meetings and their labor-intensive aspects were examined to better understand the logistical challenges involved. Results are illustrated in Figure 18.

. A significant majority (92%) of respondents believe that MTB meetings play a **crucial role in making decisions regarding patient management**. The data indicates strong support (95%) for the belief that MTB discussions **improve diagnosis accuracy by considering molecular findings**. This suggests that the molecular aspects discussed in MTB meetings are valued for their contribution to refining diagnoses. A vast majority (98%) of respondents recognize the MTB as an **important educational tool**. This suggests that the opportunity to learn from the collective discussion of cases in the MTB is highly valued by the participants.

Most respondents (61%) disagree with the idea that MTB meetings are time-consuming and delay the onset of treatment. This indicates that, despite the time involved, the overall perception is that MTB meetings **do not hinder the initiation of treatment**. However, there is still a portion (21%) who somewhat agree. majority (62%) of respondents perceive the MTB as **challenging to organize**, 21% remain neutral, indicating some uncertainty or lack of strong opinion on this matter.

The overall sentiment toward MTB meetings is overwhelmingly positive, with respondents valuing the educational and diagnostic benefits. However, concerns related to time consumption and organizational complexity should be addressed to enhance efficiency and reduce potential barriers.

There is unanimous agreement that MTBs are critically important, with a direct impact on patient treatment and, to some extent, diagnosis. However, a majority of respondents recognize that MTBs are challenging to organize and require significant effort, emphasizing the need for dedicated teams to coordinate, structure, and share their expertise. It should be noted that the responses may be biased, as they primarily come from individuals already convinced of the importance of MTBs, such as coordinators or participants.

Figure 2.18: MTB respondents insights on the effectiveness and challenges of MTB meetings.

2.10 MTB reimbursement

Among MTBs, 67.3% do not receive reimbursement, 14.3% are reimbursed through a separate tariff independent of NGS reimbursement, and 10.2% receive reimbursement tied to NGS reimbursement (Figure 19).

Figure 2.19: MTB reimbursement options across countries.

The overall findings highlight a disparity in the financial support structures for MTBs, even within the same country, suggesting a need for broader, standardized reimbursement strategies to support the sustainability and scalability of MTBs.

CONCLUSION

This survey provides a comprehensive overview of the current landscape of MTBs across Europe, highlighting significant advancements as well as persistent challenges.

Since a majority of the respondents are involved in MTBs, the data provided by the survey will offer a valuable representation of MTB practices and experiences across Europe. However, certain European countries are absent from the panel responding to the MTB section, despite participating in the survey for NGS practices. Understanding the barriers or challenges preventing MTB implementation in these regions remains crucial for fostering wider adoption and equitable access to multidisciplinary cancer care.

While the integration of NGS into routine oncology workflows and the institutionalization of MTBs underscore progress in personalized medicine, disparities in access, reimbursement, and standardization of MTBs remain critical issues.

Barriers to patient enrollment in clinical trials—such as geographic distance, lack of local support, and cohort closures—highlight the need for more accessible and flexible clinical trial structures.

Ethical concerns, particularly around patient consent and the use of genetic data, further emphasize the importance of adhering to robust regulatory frameworks to ensure patient trust and data protection.

Moreover, while the survey highlights the growing utilization of electronic health records and other digital tools to communicate NGS results and MTB recommendations, significant variability in infrastructure and adoption rates persists.

Greater harmonization in how MTBs operate, track outcomes, and communicate their impact is crucial to bridging gaps and maximizing their impact. Establishing standardized metrics for tracking patient

outcomes and recommendation implementation would enhance data transparency and provide a clearer picture of the effectiveness of MTBs.

Additionally, addressing barriers to clinical trial enrollment and ensuring robust funding and logistical support for off-label treatments are vital for maximizing the value MTBs can bring to personalized oncology care. By focusing on these areas, MTBs can better fulfill their potential to bridge the gap between molecular findings and improved patient outcomes.

Ultimately, this survey reaffirms the transformative potential of NGS and MTBs in revolutionizing cancer prevention, diagnosis, and treatment. By addressing the highlighted gaps, including the representation of missing countries, and striving for inclusivity and equity in implementation, Europe can lead the way in realizing the full promise of personalized medicine. Achieving this vision will require a sustained commitment to innovation, policy alignment, and resource allocation, ensuring that all patients benefit from these advancements, regardless of geographic or institutional constraints.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1: Institute code

COUNTRY	INSTITUTE CODE	INSTITUTE NAME
Belgium	BE01	AZ Delta
Belgium	BE02	AZ Sint-Lucas
Belgium	BE03	Clinique Saint-Luc Bouge
Belgium	BE04	Ghent University Hospital
Belgium	BE05	Grand Hôpital de Charleroi GHDC
Belgium	BE06	Imelda ziekenhuis
Belgium	BE07	IPG
Belgium	BE08	Institut Jules Bordet
Belgium	BE09	Jessa Hospital
Belgium	BE10	UZ Leuven
CZECH REPUBLIC	CZ01	Institute of Hematology and Blood Transfusion
DENMARK	DK01	Aarhus University Hospital
ESTONIA	EE01	Tartu University Hospital
FRANCE	FR01	AP-HP (Assistance Publique-Hôpitaux de Paris-Hopital Cochin)
FRANCE	FR02	Hematology laboratory Hôpital Saint-Louis, Assistance Publique-Hôpitaux de Paris (AP-HP); Université Paris-Cité
FRANCE	FR03	APHP-Robert Debré Hospital
FRANCE	FR04	Centre Antoine Lacassagne
FRANCE	FR05	CHU Besançon (University Hospital of Besançon)

FRANCE	FR06	CHU de LIMOGES
FRANCE	FR07	CHU de Poitiers
FRANCE	FR08	CHU Dijon
FRANCE	FR09	CHU SAINT-ETIENNE
FRANCE	FR10	Gustave Roussy
FRANCE	FR11	Hospices Civils de Lyon
FRANCE	FR12	Institut Curie
FRANCE	FR13	Institut de Cancérologie de Lorraine
FRANCE	FR14	university Hospital (AP-HM)
FRANCE	FR15	Versailles Hospital
GERMANY	DE01	Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin
GERMANY	DE02	Institute of pathology, RWTH University Hospital Aachen
GERMANY	DE03	Institute of Medical Genetics and Applied Genomics
GERMANY	DE04	UKSH
GERMANY	DE05	UKSH Kiel
GERMANY	DE06	University Medical Center Hamburg-Eppendorf
GERMANY	DE07	University of Cologne, Faculty of Medicine and University Hospital Cologne, Institute of Pathology
GREECE	GR01	CERTH
GREECE	GR02	GENOTYPOS MSA
GREECE	GR03	School of Medicine, University of Crete
ITALY	IT01	AUSL - IRCCS Institute of advanced technologies and care models in oncology of Reggio Emilia
ITALY	IT02	Centro di Riferimento Oncologico, CRO-Aviano IRCCS
ITALY	IT03	Fondazione Policlinico Universitario Gemelli IRCCS

ITALY	IT04	IRCCS Fondazione Pascale
ITALY	IT05	IRCCS FPO Candiolo
ITALY	IT06	IRCCS Istituto Tumori Giovanni Paolo II
ITALY	IT07	IRCCS Ospedale Policlinico San Martino
ITALY	IT08	IRCCS Regina Elena National Cancer Institute, Via Elio Chianesi 53
ITALY	IT09	IRCCS SYNLAB SDN
ITALY	IT10	Istituto Europeo di Oncologia IRCCS
ITALY	IT11	Istituto Oncologico Veneto, IRCCS
ITALY	IT12	San Raffaele Hospital
MALTA	MT01	Mater Dei Hospital c/o Ministry for Health
NETHERLANDS	NL01	Erasmus Medical Centre
NETHERLANDS	NL02	Radboudumc
NETHERLANDS	NL03	RIVM
NETHERLANDS	NL04	University Medical Center Groningen
NORWAY	NO01	Haukeland University Hospital, Section of Cancergenomics
POLAND	PL01	Maria Sklodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology
POLAND	PL02	Medical University of Gdansk
POLAND	PL03	Medical University of Warsaw
POLAND	PL04	The Children's Memorial Health Institute
PORTUGAL	PT01	Instituto nacional de Saúde DR Ricardo Jorge
SERVIA	RS01	Oncology Institute of Vojvodina
SLOVENIA	SI01	Institute of Oncology Ljubljana
SPAIN	ES01	Catalan Institute of Oncology (ICO) - Hospitalet Branch

SPAIN	ES02	Catalan Institute of Oncology of Girona
SPAIN	ES03	Complejo Asistencial de Zamora
SPAIN	ES04	Complejo Asistencial Universitario de León
SPAIN	ES05	Complejo Hospitalario Universitario de Ourense
SPAIN	ES06	Fundación Jiménez Díaz
SPAIN	ES07	Hospital Clinic Barcelona
SPAIN	ES08	Hospital Clinico de Santiago de Universitario
SPAIN	ES09	Hospital Clinico San Carlos
SPAIN	ES10	Hospital General de Segovia
SPAIN	ES11	Hospital Puerta de Hierro
SPAIN	ES12	Hospital Puerta del Mar
SPAIN	ES13	Hospital Ramón y Cajal
SPAIN	ES14	Hospital Son Espases
SPAIN	ES15	Hospital Universitari de Bellvitge
SPAIN	ES16	Hospital Universitari Germans Trias i Pujol
SPAIN	ES17	Hospital Universitari i Politècnic La Fe
SPAIN	ES18	Hospital Universitario Basurto
SPAIN	ES19	Hospital Universitario de Araba, Osakidetza (Basque Health Service)
SPAIN	ES20	Hospital Universitario Marqués de Valdecilla
SPAIN	ES21	Hospital Universitario Miguel Servet
SPAIN	ES22	Hospital Universitario San Cecilio
SPAIN	ES23	Hospital universitario toledo
SPAIN	ES24	Infanta Sofia University Hospital

SPAIN	ES25	INIBIC/CHUAC
SPAIN	ES26	Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria INCLIVA
SPAIN	ES27	IRB Barcelona
SPAIN	ES28	Laboratorio de Patología Molecular y Dianas Terapéuticas. Hospital Universitario Virgen del Rocío
SPAIN	ES29	Scientific Foundation of the Spanish Association Against Cancer
SPAIN	ES30	Vall d'Hebron Instituto de Oncología (VHIO)
UNITED KINGDOM	GB01	The University of Manchester The Christie NHS Foundation Trust

Annex 2: MTB codes

COUNTRY	MTB Code	Participating Institutes (code)	Geographical scope	MTB Name
BELGIUM	BEMTB01	BE01; BE04; BE05; BE07; BE08; BE09; BE10	National	Belgian PRECISION national Molecular Tumor Board (nMTB) (BALLETT/GeNeo)
BELGIUM	BEMTB02	BE02	Local	Local MTB AZ Sint-Lucas, local MTB AZ Alma
GERMANY	DEMTB01	DE01	Local	local MTB - Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin
GERMANY	DEMTB02	DE03	Local	local MTB at hospital Tübingen
GERMANY	DEMTB03	DE07	Local	local MTB of the University Hospital Cologne
GERMANY	DEMTB04	DE02	Local	local MTB RWTH University Hospital Aachen (Center for Integrated Oncology (CIO) Aachen)
GERMANY	DEMTB05	DE04; DE05	Local	MTB of the UKSH
ESTONIA	EEMTB01	EE01	National	national MTB in Estonia organised by Tartu University hospital
SPAIN	ESMTB01	ES01	Local	MTB Catalan Institute of Oncology for Somatic NGS
SPAIN	ESMTB02	ES01	Multi-institutional	
SPAIN	ESMTB03	ES02	Local	Comité Oncologia de Precisió - Girona
SPAIN	ESMTB04	ES03	Multi-institutional	Comité molecular de Salamanca-Zamora-Avila
SPAIN	ESMTB05	ES04	Local	Local MTB at Complejo Asistencial Universitario de León
SPAIN	ESMTB06	ES06	Local	MTB of hospitals of Quiron Madrid in Fundación Jiménez Díaz
SPAIN	ESMTB07	ES08	Local	MTB-Hospital Clinico de Santiago de Universitario
SPAIN	ESMTB08	ES09	Local	Local MTB-Hospital Clinico San Carlos
SPAIN	ESMTB09	ES11	Local	Puerta de Hierro

SPAIN	ESMTB10	ES13	Local	Comité de molecular del hospital Ramón y Cajal
SPAIN	ESMTB11	ES14	Multi-institutional	Cancer molecular diagnosis committee
SPAIN	ESMTB12	ES16	Multi-institutional	Molecular tumor board of the "Unit of molecular diagnostics, genetics and precision medicine"
SPAIN	ESMTB13	ES18	Multi-institutional	At hospital and other corporativo for all CcAa
SPAIN	ESMTB14	ES20	Multi-institutional	Regional MTB at Servicio Cantabro de Salud
SPAIN	ESMTB15	ES22	Local	Oncología Molecular Intercentros
SPAIN	ESMTB16	ES24	Multi-institutional	san carlos hospital
SPAIN	ESMTB17	ES26	Local	Comité Molecular en el Hospital Clínico de Valencia
SPAIN	ESMTB18	ES28	Local	MTB lung
FRANCE	FRMTB01	FR06	National	Multidisciplinary consultation myeloid neoplasia, lymphoid neoplasia and constitutional predisposition, adult and AYA
FRANCE	FRMTB02	FR10	Multi-institutional	multi-institutional MTB in Gustave Roussy
FRANCE	FRMTB03	FR03; FR11	National	MTB for ALL included in FMG2025 sequencing program
FRANCE	FRMTB04	FR13	Local	RCP moléculaire
FRANCE	FRMTB05	FR02	National	Refractory or Relapse Acute leukemia
FRANCE	FRMTB06	FR04	Multi-institutional	Réunion transversale de Biologie moléculaire PACA-Est
FRANCE	FRMTB07	FR14	Local	university hospital in Marseille
FRANCE	FRMTB08	FR01; FR12	National	RCP CUP (carcinoma of unknown primary)
FRANCE	FRMTB09	FR07	Local	PCP Moléculaire Poitiers
FRANCE	FRMTB10	FR09	National	PRECILA
GREECE	GRMTB01	GR01	Multi-institutional	MTB at CERTH
ITALY	ITMTB01	IT02	Local	CRO-Aviano MTB
ITALY	ITMTB02	IT04	Local	Hospital MTB - IRCCS Fondazione Pascale
ITALY	ITMTB03	IT08	Local	IRE MTB

ITALY	ITMTB04	IT05	Local	local MTB at Candiolo IRCC FPO
ITALY	ITMTB05	IT07	Local	Local MTB at IRCCS Policlinico San Martino, Genova Italy
ITALY	ITMTB06	IT03	Multi-institutional	MTB Policlinico Gemelli
ITALY	ITMTB07	IT06	Multi-institutional	Region Puglia MTB
ITALY	ITMTB08	IT10	Multi-institutional	Regional MTB of Lombardy
ITALY	ITMTB09	IT11	Multi-institutional	Regione Veneto MTB
NETHERLANDS	NLMTB01	NL02	Multi-institutional	MTB of Radboudumc
NETHERLANDS	NLMTB02	NL04	Multi-institutional	regional UMCG MTB
NORWAY	NOMTB01	NO01	National	InPreD national molecular Multi Disiplinary Tumorbord (mol-MDT)
POLAND	PLMTB01	PL01	Local	MTB at Maria Sklodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology
POLAND	PLMTB02	PL02	Local	local MTB at University Clinical Centre-Medical University of Gdansk
POLAND	PLMTB03	PL03	Local	MTB at the Medical University of Warsaw
SLOVENIA	SIMTB01	SI01	Local	MTB at the Institute of Oncology Ljubljana

WP8.4_CAN.HEAL Annex II

In the CAN.HEAL

European project "Building the EU Cancer and Public Health Genomics platform", we are interested in reporting the role of Molecular Tumor Boards (MTB) addressing patients to personalized medicine. Could you please spare a few minutes to fulfill this questionnaire?

1. Name

2. **Specialty**

Mark only one oval.

Medical Oncologist

Pathologist

Molecular Biologist

Geneticist

Other

3. Center

4. City

5. Country

6. Age

7. Gender

Mark only one oval.

Female

Male

8. 1. Do you have access to NGS at your center in your clinical practice?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

9. 2. Is NGS testing performed exclusively on the tumor, or is it also conducted on plasma (liquid biopsy)?

Mark only one oval.

Tumor only

Liquid and Solid biopsy

None

2.1. If your answer to question 2 was 'None':

10. 2.1.A. Are you able to refer cases to other centers for NGS testing?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

11. 2.1.B. Has any clinical pathway been established, or has an agreement been reached with other centers to do so?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

12. 2.1.C. Is there any protocol in place to define which patients are considered candidates to NGS testing?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

2.2. If your answer to question 2 was 'Tumor only' or "Liquid and Solid biopsy":

13. 2.2.A. Do you regularly attend the MTB meetings?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

14. 2.2.B. Are all cases discussed in the MTB?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

15. 2.2.C. Are the molecular reports available uploaded to the medical chart?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

16. 2.2.D. Are those notes collected during the discussion available in the medical chart?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

17. 2.2.E. Are you happy with the turn-around time?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

18. 2.2.F. Could you estimate the average turn-around time by indicating the estimated number of days?

19. 2.2.G. Is reflex testing (requested by a pathologist) implemented in your practice?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

20. 3. Do you have an electronic database to collect molecular and clinicopathological results?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

21. 4. Do you think that collecting those results will be useful?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

22. 5. Would you be interested in being able to benchmark and compare your results with other centers?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

23. 6. Which percentage of patients have an actionable alteration detected by NGS?
(If you do not know the percentage, please answer "Unknown")

24. 7. Could you provide an absolute number per year? (If you do not know the absolute number, please answer "Unknown")

25. 8. Were these responses documented by a source of information?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

26. 9. Do you think that a fraction of patients with actionable alterations is not receiving the therapy recommended by the MTB?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Unknown

27. 10. Do you think that having NGS testing increased access to targeted therapies?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

28. 10.1. Which are the main reasons? Multi-response

Check all that apply.

Lack of access to specific treatment

Lack of clinical trials information

Poor performance status or short life expectancy

Treatment physician decision

Patient decision

Others:

Other: _____

29. 11. Do you consider that some genomic alterations are being detected more frequently by using NGS vs single gene methods?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

30. 11.1. If your answer to question 11 was 'Yes', Which?

31. 12. Do you consider that some genomic alterations are being detected less frequently by using NGS vs single gene methods?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

32. 12.1. If your answer to question 12 was 'Yes', Which?

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